

INTERVIEW WITH E.R. YESCOMBE¹⁻²

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RDAI – After reading your book,³ we came across different hard cases that we have experienced in our professional life and most of these questions are based on those experiences that we have had. We would very much like to have your point of view on those matters and to know a little more about your professional background. You literally wrote the book on the matter of project finance and yet you graduated from Oxford University Law School. How did you end up working with project finance?

E.R. Yescombe – Because in the days when I was taking a law degree, most of my contemporaries didn't actually become lawyers. They became other things. One became a printer, other became an architect. The law in those days was not the kind of big money profession is today and I wasn't really that attracted to it. To be honest, the reason I became a banker was that I had traveled while a student in India and I found I could work for a British bank in India. So I liked the idea of going to live in India. It's not a very good reason, but that's why I became a banker. And the term project finance didn't exist when I became a banker. In the 1980s I worked for what is now MUFG, which is the largest Japanese bank and

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 2. Entrevista concedida em 23 de agosto de 2018 na sede do Instituto Brasileiro de Estudos Jurídicos da Infraestrutura – IBEJI, em São Paulo.
 3. *Principles of Project Finance*, 2nd edition (San Diego: Academic Press, 2014). Portuguese translation to be published [...]